

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Essential time series characteristics for human motion analysis based on Self-Organizing Map clustering

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Abstract

Background: Accurate classification of physical exercise is essential for individualised training and rehabilitation. Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) offer a data-driven way to cluster movement patterns. **Objective:** To extract the most informative acceleration- and angular-velocity features from children's movements and use SOM to build a map and visualize the similarity structure among exercises based on trunk dynamics. **Methods:** Eighty-one children (9–11 years) performed eight dynamic tasks while 3-D accelerometers and gyroscopes recorded kinematics. The performed tasks are Shuttle Run, Crawling, Progressive Cone Shuttle Run, Ring Collection and Placement Run, 10x Position Change Drill, 10x Head-to-Foot Hoop Crawl, 10x Bench Jumping, Crawling (repeat). Data were collected in a single session using one back-mounted inertial sensor; the SOM solution with seven super-clusters yielded a mean Silhouette width of 0.36, indicating moderate cluster separation. Time series (records) were described with Recurrence Quantification Analysis, autocorrelation and Fourier transforms. XGBoost selected 27 key features that guided SOM optimisation and clustering. **Results:** With 27 optimised features, the SOM exceeded 90% accuracy and organised the seven movement tasks, including one repeated task, into seven coherent clusters. For instance, 10x Head-to-Foot Hoop Crawl and 4x 10m Shuttle Run exercises were found to differ primarily due to the presence of locomotion and rapid acceleration changes in the latter, while the former exhibited higher angular velocity during trunk bending. 10x Position Change Drill exercise was characterized by dynamic transitions between standing, prone, and supine positions, whereas Crawling exercise involved steady, low acceleration movements. **Conclusions:** Advanced feature extraction combined with XGBoost-guided selection yields a compact, informative descriptor set that enables SOM to map children's exercises with high accuracy. This workflow offers a practical, data-driven approach to mapping and organizing exercises based on similarity in trunk dynamics, rather than a discrete classification.

Keywords: accelerometer, classification, children, gyroscope, feature extraction, physical exercise

Introduction

Accurate classification of physical exercise is fundamental to sports science and rehabilitation. It enables personalised interventions that optimise health outcomes by matching exercise modalities to individual needs (Garber et al., 2011; Posadzki et al., 2020). Systematic categorisation also supports the modelling of competitive conditions, the simulation of real-world performance, and the planning of individualised rehabilitation programmes while accounting for health status and physical capacity (Townsend, 2022). For example, it guides coaches in selecting sprint drills that enhance short-distance acceleration and plyometric exercises that build the explosive power required for jumping—key attributes for track-and-field athletes (Myrvang & van den Tillaar, 2024). It likewise informs the prescription of resistance training to increase bone density and of activities such as swimming or yoga, which, at appropriate intensities, promote cardiovascular and joint health (Faíl et al., 2022; Posadzki et al., 2020; Turner & Robling, 2003).

A well-defined typology aids in selecting exercises that align with fitness goals while avoiding those that may be unsuitable (Garber et al., 2011). Grouping exercises by similarity also facilitates their planned variation, sustains long-term motivation and prevents monotony (Eather et al., 2023). For example, alternating between high-intensity and low-intensity exercises can keep participants engaged and motivated. In essence, understanding the specific effects and benefits associated with various types of physical exercise guides decision-making and optimizes outcomes across diverse domains.

In this context, the Self-Organizing Map (SOM) emerges as a promising tool for movement classification and clustering in sports and rehabilitation (Bohari et al., 2016; Parra-Rodríguez et al., 2022; Su, 2015). SOM is an unsupervised neural network algorithm that excels at projecting high-dimensional data into low-dimensional maps while preserving the inherent data topology (Parra-Rodríguez et al., 2022). It captures irregular forms and provides an understanding of the dataset's structure (Yin,

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2008), thus offering a flexible approach to analyzing complex data and extracting meaningful insights. However, a limitation of SOM is its slow convergence rate and reduced classification accuracy when employing a rectangular lattice topology and Euclidean distance measurement (Bohari et al., 2016). Potential solutions to this limitation include experimenting with different lattice topologies or distance metrics to improve accuracy and efficiency.

Training SOMs with datasets containing information on physical exercises, including data on acceleration and angular changes, enables the model to map similar exercises to proximate locations on the map (Mo et al., 2022). Mapping similar exercises close to each other on the map is beneficial for understanding exercise patterns and making informed decisions on training and rehabilitation interventions. Thanks to these properties, SOMs have been successfully used to assess rehabilitation progress by clustering similar movements (Sarwat et al., 2020; Su, 2015).

Characterising acceleration dynamics during exercise is therefore pivotal for performance optimisation and injury prevention. A detailed understanding of movement biomechanics informs strategies to minimise joint stress and injury risk – issues central to sports medicine, orthopaedics, and rehabilitation (Amadio & Serrão, 2011; Dutt, 2018; Priego-Quesada, 2021; Suhartoyo et al., 2020). Inertial measurement units (IMUs) are widely used to capture such kinematic signatures in field conditions. Multi-sensor systems (e.g., sensors at the wrist, ankle, waist, trunk) are known to improve activity recognition and capture limb-specific kinematics (Janidarmian et al., 2017; Shoaib et al., 2016). That said, multi-sensor layouts are more invasive, harder to standardise in classrooms or early rehabilitation, and more prone to missing data and poor placement when used by children. For practical deployment in physical education or clinical screening, a minimal single-sensor approach may be preferable even if it sacrifices segment-level detail. We therefore focus on the feasibility question: can we distinguish exercises using only a single trunk-mounted sensor, in realistic school-gym conditions, and can we do so in a way that remains interpretable to a practitioner?

These considerations raise two questions: (i) Can physical exercises be typologically distinguished on the basis of dynamic movement parameters recorded from one trunk-mounted sensor in a real-world setting? and (ii) Which features characterise typologically similar exercises and differentiate distinct ones? Addressing these questions demands a practical, robust methodology for classifying exercises from execution dynamics, which this study seeks to provide through SOM clustering.

SOM preserves topology in a low-dimensional map, which aids interpretability for coaches and therapists and works well with modest datasets (Kohonen, 2001; Wehrens & Kruisselbrink, 2018). While deep or margin-based classifiers (e.g., CNN/LSTM/SVM) can excel on large multi-sensor datasets, they require extensive labels and infrastructure; multi-sensor studies generally report gains from combining body locations (e.g., wrist/ankle/waist), but at the cost of complexity (Janidarmian et al., 2017; Shoaib et al., 2016).

Therefore, the aim of this study was to identify the key features from children's acceleration and angular-velocity time series and use a self-organizing map (SOM) to map and visualize the similarity structure among physical exercises.

Focusing on children's movements is crucial, as it provides insights into how these dynamics affect developmental motor skills vital to both athletic and everyday activities. While SOM has been applied to exercise typology before, this study innovates by emphasising execution dynamics. We explore how distinctive movement patterns reveal relationships and distinctions among exercise types and present a novel pipeline for feature extraction and exercise recognition.

Methods

Study design

For this cross-sectional (single session) study, a series of seven movement tasks, with one task repeated twice, was designed using a standardized protocol (Cuberek et al., 2024). All children were instructed identically to perform the tasks sequentially and as quickly as possible while maintaining correct technique on a predetermined course. The exercises were completed in the same fixed order by all participants. The task battery was purposefully assembled to span a broad range of movement demands that are common in youth physical testing and sport participation and that are expected to produce clearly distinguishable accelerometry patterns. Specifically, the sequence included: (i) upright running tasks dominated by cyclical lower-limb impacts but differing in intensity and structure (short sprint-type shuttle running vs. a progressive shuttle run with repeated accelerations and decelerations), (ii) a running task augmented by object handling (placing and collecting rings) to introduce intermittent trunk flexion, upper-limb involvement, and brief pauses superimposed on locomotion, (iii) a plyometric task (repeated two-foot jumps) characterised by prominent vertical impact peaks and regular take-off/landing cycles, (iv) a non-locomotor position-change sequence (stand–prone–roll–stand) designed to elicit large body reorientations with episodic, non-periodic acceleration patterns, and (v) a coordination-focused task performed predominantly in place (hoop pass from head to feet) involving controlled whole-body adjustments. In addition, slow locomotion in a low body position (crawling) was included to contrast upright gait mechanics with a markedly different centre-of-mass height and limb support pattern. The order of tasks was arranged to alternate activities expected to elicit higher versus lower movement speeds and overall acceleration magnitude (e.g., running/jumping interspersed with slower or predominantly in-place tasks), thereby varying the instantaneous movement intensity across the sequence rather than progressing monotonically. Crawling was performed twice – once early and once later in the sequence – to capture potential context- and fatigue-related changes in the same nominal task and to examine whether self-organizing maps group the repeated movement consistently despite accumulated exertion. The tasks are described in detail in [Table A1](#).

During completion of all tasks, data on bodily acceleration and angular velocity were collected using 3-axial accelerometer and gyroscope sensors, which characterise individual movement behaviour during the performed tasks.

The data were analysed within a comprehensive framework that combined traditional statistics with Recurrence Quantification Analysis (RQA; Webber & Marwan, 2015), autocorrelation analysis, and the Fourier transform to uncover latent temporal patterns. This framework supplied the feature space for constructing a SOM for activity prediction based on dynamic movement parameters. Subsequently, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost; Chen & Guestrin, 2016) removed redundant features, thereby increasing SOM efficiency and predictive quality. The optimal number of SOM superclusters was determined with the Silhouette method (Rousseeuw, 1987).

All processing and analyses were conducted in Python (Version 3.8.10; <https://www.python.org>) and R (Version 4.3.2; <https://www.R-project.org>).

Participants

Eighty-one children aged 9–11 years (36 girls with an average body mass index of $17.3 \pm 3.45 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and 45 boys with an average body mass index of $18.6 \pm 3.56 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) took part in the study. Pupils from two classes at two primary schools were recruited during regular physical education lessons. Considering that the movement tasks reflected standard activities commonly performed during physical education classes, no specific inclusion or exclusion criteria for the exercises were applied. Legal guardians received written information detailing the study's purpose and data-collection procedures and subsequently provided signed informed consent. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Physical Culture, Palacký University Olomouc, under reference number 101/2023.

Measurements

Individual movement data were recorded with an Axivity AX6 device (Axivity Ltd.), which integrates tri-axial accelerometer and gyroscope sensors oriented along the mediolateral (x), craniocaudal (y) and sagittal (z) axes. The device was placed between the shoulder blades of the participants. Each participant generated six synchronous time series (three acceleration, three angular velocity) sampled at 100 Hz; dynamic ranges were $\pm 16 \text{ g}$ for acceleration and $\pm 2000^\circ\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ for angular velocity. Recordings for the eight-exercise sequence lasted 7.1–86.4 s (mean 21.9 s), depending on the tasks.

Prior to each of the eight movement tasks, participants paused briefly in an upright stance while the back-mounted sensor was tapped three times. This procedure produced a distinctive, readily identifiable pattern in the accelerometer trace, allowing each exercise to be delineated. Individual tasks were annotated manually in the raw data, and the tap segments were subsequently removed.

Data analysis

In order to filter non-informative features, five feature sets were generated, each capturing time-series characteristics from a distinct analytical perspective (Table 1). RQA (Webber & Marwan, 2015) was applied to identify recurring patterns and quantify their frequency and duration, using the Chaos01 (Version 1.2.1; <https://cran.r-project.org/package=Chaos01>) and NonlinearTseries (Version 0.2.12; <https://cran.r-project.org/package=nonlinearTseries>) R packages. All parameters are listed in Table 2. For both sensors, the RQA settings were identical except for the threshold/neighbourhood size (ϵ), computed separately as the mean standard deviation across all participants, trials and axes. This yielded $\epsilon = 0.753$ for the accelerometer and $\epsilon = 96.416$ for the gyroscope sensors. Further implementation details are available in Patrikei et al. (2024).

The five feature sets comprised: (i) RQA metrics; (ii) autocorrelation-based descriptors; (iii) Fourier (spectral) features; (iv) a combined set of RQA, autocorrelation and spectral metrics; and (v) the full output of the *ComprehensiveFCParameters* function from the *tsfresh* Python library (Christ et al., 2018), see Table 1. These features target complementary biomechanical properties. RQA-based metrics quantify signal determinism and recurrence structure, which relate to movement regularity and postural control strategies. Autocorrelation-based variables capture the periodicity and rhythm of repeated actions, such as cyclical trunk oscillations during shuttle running or crawling.

Table 1 Overview of extracted feature sets

Set	Names
Recurrence Quantitative Analysis (RQA)	recurrence rate; determinism; ratio; average recurrence length; maximal recurrence length; divergence; laminarity; trapping time; longest vertical line; total number of recurrence points; recurrence points on the diagonal lines of length of $\geq l_{\text{min}}$; count of diagonal lines of length of length $\geq l_{\text{min}}$; recurrence points on the vertical lines of length of length $\geq l_{\text{min}}$; trend of vertical lines of length of length $\geq l_{\text{min}}$
Autocorrelation	autocorrelation for lags 0–9; aggregated autocorrelation (using mean, median, variance); partial autocorrelation for lags 0–9
Spectral	aggregated statistics of the Fast Fourier Transform magnitude spectrum (using centroid, variance, skew, kurtosis); approximate entropy; fourier coefficients from 0 to 99 (with attributes real, imag, abs, and angle); entropy of the frequency spectrum; power spectral density values estimated (using Welch's method)
Mix	all the above features combined
All tsfresh features	output of ComprehensiveFCParameters() function from the tsfresh library

Table 2 Recurrence quantitative analysis parameters

Function argument	Value
Embedding dimension (dim)	3
Embedding lag (lag)	time series lengths
Neighbourhood size (eps)	accelerometer (0.753), gyroscope (96.416)
All minimal length of line to be considered for recurrence line (l_{min})	20

Frequency-domain descriptors capture energy at different frequencies, reflecting impact intensity, abrupt redirections of the centre of mass, and neuromuscular demand (Amadio & Serrão, 2011; Priego-Quesada, 2021; Suhartoyo et al., 2020). Together, these features describe whether a child is producing smooth, rhythmically repeated, high-force movements (e.g., shuttle run with rapid turns) or more controlled, posture-dominated transitions (e.g., repeated prone-to-stand changes).

The features (RQA, autocorrelation, spectrum) were computed directly from normalized time series (100 Hz) without applying subsequent noise suppression, so as to reflect realistic deployment conditions in school settings where advanced on-site processing is not required.

Then, dimensionality was reduced with Extreme Gradient Boosting implemented in the XGBoost R package (Version 1.7.6.1; <https://cran.r-project.org/package=xgboost>). Feature importance was quantified by Gain, the accuracy improvement contributed by each variable to the ensemble. Iteratively ranking features by Gain enabled us to identify a compact subset of predictors that retained discriminative power while limiting redundancy. This step served two purposes: (i) it improved downstream SOM efficiency by reducing the dimensionality of the input space; and (ii) it mitigated overfitting by discarding weak or noisy predictors before training the SOM.

A two-dimensional SOM was trained with the kohonen R package (Wehrens & Buydens, 2007) and visualised using aweSOM R package (Version 1.3; <https://cran.r-project.org/package=aweSOM>). aweSOM also reports model-quality indices derived from Kohonen (2001). The SOM was implemented as a 5 × 5 hexagonal grid. This grid size was selected to balance two competing requirements. On one hand, the map needed to be large enough to represent meaningful distinctions between exercises without forcing them into the same neuron (Kohonen, 2001; Vesanto & Alhoniemi, 2000). On the other hand, a substantially larger map would have fragmented the available samples across many sparsely populated units, reducing interpretability. We chose a hexagonal (rather than rectangular) topology because hexagonal neighbourhoods reduce directional

bias and improve local neighbourhood preservation when mapping high-dimensional data into two dimensions (Kohonen, 2001; Wehrens & Krusselbrink, 2018). The combination of modest map size and hexagonal topology was therefore intended to maximise interpretability without severely sacrificing resolution.

Cluster validity was assessed with the Silhouette method, where higher scores indicate tighter, better-separated clusters and a score of 1 denotes perfect assignment (Anh Tu, 2019). Because Quantisation Error and Silhouette width vary with feature dimensionality, overall classification accuracy was additionally used to compare SOM models built on different feature sets. Classification performance was reported from cross-validation on held-out samples, rather than on the training data, to limit optimistic bias (Arlot & Celisse, 2010).

The presented workflow is publicly available at the publicly available repository [code.it4i.cz ADAS/Movement-classification](https://code.it4i.cz/ADAS/movement-classification) (<https://code.it4i.cz/ADAS/movement-classification>), together with the original dataset (Cuberek et al., 2024).

Results

Five feature sets were generated for each of the three orthogonal axes of both the accelerometer and the gyroscope (Table 1). Feature importance was assessed with an XGBoost model implemented in R. The importance of the features, quantified by gain – the accuracy improvement contributed by each variable – served to rank the predictors. SOM models were then trained with different numbers of features ($k = 2–35$), and their classification accuracy was recorded. The used features served as input for clustering with a SOM; all XGBoost and SOM hyper-parameters are provided in Table 3.

Prototype vectors from each SOM were grouped into super-clusters by applying partitioning-around-medoids (PAM, k -medians) to the codebook vectors; hierarchical clustering yielded comparable structures. The optimal number of clusters was assessed using the Silhouette Coefficient, Calinski–Harabasz Index, and Davies–Bouldin Index. For

Table 3 XGBoost and Self-Organizing Map (SOM) parameters with descriptions

Parameter	Value	Description
XGBoost		
Booster	gbtree	type of booster to use (gbtree for tree-based models)
Eta	0.3	learning rate; controls the contribution of each tree
Gamma	0	minimum loss reduction required for a split
Max depth	6	maximum depth of a tree; controls model complexity
Min child weight	1	minimum sum of weights for child nodes to prevent overfitting
Subsample	1	fraction of data samples used to grow each tree
Colsample bytree	1	fraction of features used for each tree, useful for reducing overfitting
nrounds	min logloss	number of boosting rounds; stopping criteria based on minimum log loss
SOM		
Grid size	5×5	size of the SOM grid
Grid type	hexagonal	shape of the SOM grid units (hexagonal or rectangular)
Alpha	0.05–0.01	initial learning rate, which decays during training
Distance function	sum of squares	metric used to measure distance between nodes in the SOM
rlen	1000	number of iterations during training

each metric, the optimal number of clusters varied (see Figure 1). Nevertheless, since seven different exercises were analyzed, we selected this value as the final number of clusters. This choice is supported by the Silhouette method, which indicates seven as the optimal number of clusters, while the other two indices also yield satisfactory values.

Figure 2 depicts the 5x5 SOM trained on 27 features; background shading marks the seven super-clusters obtained by partitioning-around-medoids, while the pie charts show the exercise composition of individual neurons. In the lower-left red region, virtually every unit represents the 10x Head-to-Foot Hoop Crawl task, with only an

Figure 1 Depiction of Calinski-Harabasz Index, Davies-Bouldin Index, and Silhouette coefficient for different number of clusters

Figure 2 The resulting 5x5 Self-Organizing Map network, based on 27 time-series features, illustrates the classification of movement tasks. Within each hexagon, circles indicate the tasks assigned to that node, with circle size proportional to the number of measurements mapped to the hexagon. The background color of each hexagon denotes the corresponding super-class (resulting cluster).

occasional instance of the Ring Collection and Placement Run. This pairing reflects smooth, largely stationary upper-body coordination. The blue zone occupying the lower right contains all crawling trials (performed as the second and eighth tasks), capturing a uniform, low-amplitude ground-level locomotion pattern. Immediately above, the mid-left green area is dominated by the Ring Collection and Placement Run, whose slalom locomotion, coupled with object manipulation, distinguishes it from neighbouring activities. The central purple patch consists mainly of 10x Bench Jumping, interspersed with a few 10x Position Change Drill trials. The apricot sector toward the upper left is composed solely of the Position Change Drill, characterised by rapid transitions among standing, prone and supine positions executed in place. In the top centre, yellow cells correspond to the Progressive Cone Shuttle Run, distinguished by high-intensity, multidirectional sprint bursts. In contrast, the upper-right brown corner is reserved for the straight-line 4x 10 m Shuttle Run – the fastest activity in the set. Overall, the SOM map reveals a clear spatial segregation of movement tasks, with inter-cluster distances mirroring biomechanical similarity and thus confirming the feasibility of classifying exercises from accelerometer- and gyroscope-derived data.

Classification performance was evaluated with cross-validation. The best result – an accuracy exceeding 90% – was obtained when the SOM was trained on the 27 most informative features and partitioned into 7 super-clusters. The coexistence of >90% classification accuracy with a moderate Silhouette width (0.36) suggests that, although cluster boundaries in the reduced feature space are not perfectly separated, the resulting super-clusters are still discriminative enough to assign most trials to the correct class. We interpret this as follows: (i) distinct activities such as shuttle running versus floor-based crawling are captured robustly at the trunk level, whereas (ii) exercises that share similar trunk-dominant control strategies (e.g., repeated prone-to-stand transitions vs. crawling) exhibit partial overlap. This is biomechanically sensible, given that both involve low centre-of-mass manoeuvres and repeated trunk flexion/rotation. This observation is further supported by the calculation of the Davies–Bouldin Index (DBI), which measures the ratio of within-cluster scatter to between-cluster separation. In other words, it assesses how compact the clusters are internally and how well separated they are from one another (Davies & Bouldin, 1979). For the resulting SOM model, the DBI value is 0.827, indicating acceptable clustering quality (DBI < 0.5: very good separation, 0.5–1.0: acceptable clustering, >1.0: poor clustering).

Discussion

This study focuses on the typology of physical exercises in children using the SOM method, utilizing dynamic movement parameters obtained from time series data of accelerometer and gyroscope readings in three primary axes (x, y, and z). Specifically, the aim was to identify the optimal characteristics of time series of acceleration and changes in angular velocity during specific physical exercises in

children and assess the degree of similarity between them based on these characteristics.

Empirical data were collected from an IMU device placed on the child's back during eight defined physical exercises. These exercises were intentionally selected to include various types of movements, such as locomotion and object manipulation, allowing us to analyze different dynamic patterns. We expected that the SOM model would reveal varying degrees of similarity between these activities.

The results showed that direct application of SOM to raw data without feature engineering is not effective. This finding underscores the importance of sophisticated feature engineering methods such as RQA, autocorrelation, and spectral analysis to uncover hidden patterns in motion data. Furthermore, Jain and Kanhangad (2018) demonstrate that the use of both time-domain and frequency-domain features significantly improves the accuracy of activity classification. Similarly, Yang and Hsu (2010) emphasize the necessity of various feature engineering techniques to extract meaningful features from the raw accelerometer data, which aligns with our findings. These methods allowed us to better understand the dynamics of the tasks performed and provide a robust basis for the subsequent classification of the exercises using SOM. These findings confirm that multifaceted feature extraction is essential to improve the precision and reliability of exercise classification models (Kohonen, 1990).

Using the XGBoost model for selecting optimal features significantly improved the performance of SOM. Iterative feature selection based on their importance, measured by the Gain parameter, allowed for enhanced predictive capabilities of the model. In agreement with Vesanto and Alhoniemi (2000), it appears that incorporating machine learning techniques such as XGBoost into the feature selection process optimizes classification and leads to better results.

The assembled SOM (5 × 5, based on 27-time series features) model includes seven superclusters, each almost exclusively representing a single exercise. Cross-validated classification accuracy exceeded 90%, indicating that, despite partial overlap in movement patterns between certain drills, the selected feature set captured sufficient information to assign most trials to the correct class. At the same time, the mean Silhouette width of 0.36 indicates only moderate separation between clusters. A moderate Silhouette score is expected when exercises share core mechanical elements – for example, both Crawling and 10x Position Change Drill involve repeated close-to-ground manoeuvres with substantial trunk flexion and rotation. In such cases, trunk-mounted signals encode broadly similar postural transitions and load transfer, which naturally reduces inter-cluster distances. We therefore interpret the Silhouette score not as a methodological failure but as evidence that some drills are biomechanically related and may represent variations on a common neuromotor demand rather than completely distinct movement classes.

The relative positions of the super-clusters across the SOM corresponded to the similarity of the exercises in terms of their movement content. This includes factors

such as the type of locomotion, changes in direction, explosive position changes of the trunk, and floor-contact demands. On the diagonals, the most distinct pairs are 10x Head-to-Foot Hoop Crawl vs 4x 10 m Shuttle Run and 10x Position Change Drill versus Crawling/Crawling (repeat). The main biomechanical difference in the first pair is the presence of high-speed changes of direction, impact peaks, and deceleration phases in the shuttle run, contrasted with controlled, low-centre-of-mass manoeuvring in the hoop crawl. The second pair differs mainly in that the 10x Position Change Drill involves repeated rapid transfers between supine, prone, kneeling and standing. In contrast, Crawling represents a more continuous locomotor pattern while maintaining a low centre of mass. These distinctions align with known developmental demands in late childhood, where rapid whole-body reorientation and centre-of-mass control are still being refined.

The differences between clusters observed in the SOM, which represent the given exercises, are fully consistent with the movement content of these activities. Considering the first mentioned pair, the main difference in movement content between the exercises is the presence of locomotion and rapid changes in acceleration direction (primarily) in the sagittal plane for the locomotion exercise 4x 10m Shuttle Run versus significant changes in angular velocity during trunk bends, with the individual standing relatively stable in one place for the “non-locomotion” exercise 10x Head-to-Foot Hoop Crawl. For the second pair of exercises, the difference again lies in the presence of locomotion in the case of crawling, characterized by low acceleration values mainly in the sagittal plane of the trunk. In contrast, the 10x Position Change Drill is characterized by very dynamic transitions between three positions (standing, lying on the stomach, and lying on the back), which the individual performs in one place. The direction and magnitude of the resultant acceleration vector and angular velocity differ significantly between this pair. Another difference in movement content for both pairs is the difference in the period of complex movement elements. While locomotion exercises involve shorter, more frequent elements (locomotion steps), the period for positional changes comprises the entire cycle, of which there are ten in both cases.

The results also indicate that the individual dynamic patterns of performed exercises have less variability than the variability among different exercises, which allows for their typology based on their dynamic execution. However, the presented SOM model also shows that with specific characteristics of time series, the individual dynamic pattern of movement in a particular exercise can appear similar to that of a different exercise performed by another individual. This observation raises an important question: whether this similarity is a limitation of the SOM model or if the movement dynamics between two individuals are genuinely similar across different exercises. To address this question, future research should focus on thorough validation and parameter optimization of the SOM model. This process would help determine if the observed similarities are due to model limitations or if they reflect true similarities in movement dynamics between individuals.

Our findings are practically beneficial in several respects. The similarity of dynamic movement patterns identified through the SOM model has the potential for application in various health and sports areas where physical exercises form the content of targeted interventions. Importantly, the way the SOM differentiated the exercise tasks (including their neighbourhood relationships on the map) was largely consistent with the expected qualitative differences in the nature of the movements, which provides preliminary support for the interpretability of the identified structure. Nevertheless, this should not be considered a formal validation, and further work is needed to verify whether the observed similarities reflect true shared movement dynamics or model-related effects. Based on our results, it can be assumed that dynamically similar exercises may have the potential to enrich movement programs and increase the variability of exercise selection. This could offer individuals a broader range of exercise options and potentially support training variability and motivation, although these outcomes were not directly assessed in the present study. Integrating SOM-based systems with real-time monitoring and feedback tools represents a promising avenue for future research. Such systems could provide immediate feedback to users, leading to increased effectiveness of exercise programs and rehabilitation protocols (Yang & Hsu, 2010).

The present findings suggest two concrete application areas. First, exercise selection, progression, and variation. Because SOM places biomechanically similar tasks near one another, this approach suggests the possibility of identifying alternative exercises that elicit comparable trunk dynamics. This can be used to (i) increase the variety of exercises used without abandoning a targeted neuromotor demand (Eather et al., 2023), (ii) tailor exercise difficulty to a child's current movement capacity, or (iii) avoid painful movements while preserving key mechanical stimuli in rehabilitation. For example, if two movement tasks cluster closely, substituting one for the other may help maintain comparable trunk dynamics while potentially changing perceived difficulty/joint loading (to be verified in future studies). This aligns with recommendations for progression, variation and adherence in youth physical activity interventions (Eather et al., 2023). Second, monitoring of execution quality over time. Prior work has shown that SOM-based representations can be used to visualise motor recovery trajectories in patients after neurological injury (Sarwat et al., 2020; Su, 2015). By analogy, a longitudinal application of the present pipeline could track whether a child's execution of, for example, the 10x Position Change Drill becomes more similar to the prototype pattern of age-matched peers after targeted core-stability or agility training. Such use cases require repeated-measures designs, which were not part of the present study. Still, they illustrate how the map output could serve as a monitoring tool in paediatric rehabilitation or return-to-play testing.

Methodological considerations and limitations

Several methodological considerations must be acknowledged explicitly. First, all kinematic data were obtained from a single trunk-mounted IMU. This choice reflects a

pragmatic balance between biomechanical fidelity and ecological feasibility in classes of physical education. However, it necessarily neglects limb-specific kinematics, such as arm swing during ring collection or unilateral push-off forces during bench jumps. Prior literature shows that combining sensors from multiple body locations (e.g., wrist, ankle, waist) generally improves human activity recognition and robustness across tasks (Janidarmian et al., 2017; Shoib et al., 2016). Our findings should therefore be interpreted as a conservative lower bound on what could be captured with a richer sensor setup and not as evidence that one trunk sensor is universally optimal.

Second, the study used a single-session, cross-sectional design. Consequently, we cannot evaluate whether the SOM-derived typology remains stable across repeated trials, on different days, or after training interventions. Such longitudinal reliability is crucial if the method is to be used for rehabilitation monitoring or developmental assessment. Repeated-measures designs will be necessary to determine intra-individual consistency and sensitivity to change over time.

Third, although classification accuracy exceeded 90%, the average Silhouette width of 0.36 indicates only moderate cluster separation, suggesting that some exercises share partially overlapping trunk-dynamics signatures. From a methodological standpoint, this raises the possibility that apparent high accuracy could in part reflect overfitting to subtle differences in the specific dataset. We attempted to limit this risk by (i) performing XGBoost-based feature reduction before SOM training to suppress noisy predictors, and (ii) evaluating performance using cross-validation on held-out samples (Arlot & Celisse, 2010). Nevertheless, some residual overfitting cannot be excluded because we did not test the trained model on fully independent external data. It should also be noted that, in our study, the SOM method was not benchmarked against other approaches (e.g., convolutional neural network, long short-term memory network, support vector machine, or *k*-means); therefore, it cannot be concluded that SOM is the optimal method – it was only demonstrated to be feasible, interpretable, and practically applicable in our setting.

Fourth, although we provide detailed descriptions of each exercise (Table A1) and now explicitly report the station order, environmental setup, and standardised verbal instructions, some procedural factors typical of laboratory biomechanics studies – such as full randomisation of task order or strict control of fatigue – were intentionally relaxed to preserve ecological validity in the physical education setting. This is a trade-off between internal experimental control and real-world applicability. The resulting data are more ecologically valid for school-based movement screening and potentially for rehabilitation triage but somewhat less controlled than laboratory data.

Finally, our analysis centred on trunk dynamics as a proxy for whole-body control demands in late childhood. Children aged 9–11 years are still refining inter-limb coordination, postural transitions, and rapid redirection of the centre of mass during high-speed locomotion. The ability of the selected features (e.g., determinism, spectral

bandwidth) to capture these developmental aspects of motor control is encouraging. Still, broader age ranges and clinical groups (e.g., children with motor impairments) should be examined before generalising these findings. Therefore, the results cannot be directly generalized to older adolescents, adults, or populations with substantially different motor fitness without further verification; this study does not provide evidence of cross-population generalizability.

Conclusions

The results of this study indicate that the direct application of the SOM method to raw data without prior processing was ineffective, highlighting the necessity for advanced feature extraction methods such as RQA, autocorrelation, and spectral analysis. Using XGBoost for feature selection significantly improved SOM performance, highlighting the value of integrating machine learning into this workflow to map and organize physical exercises based on similarity in trunk dynamics.

The constructed SOM model, based on 27 time-series features, successfully distinguished between various physical exercises, allowing for their classification into specific movement pattern groups. The findings also suggest that exercises with similar dynamic characteristics can be grouped into adjacent clusters in the SOM, which holds potential practical applications in training and rehabilitation programs.

It should be noted, however, that the limited number of subjects tested and the SOM model's ability to classify nonlinear data may constrain the generalizability of these conclusions. Future research should, therefore, include larger and more diverse populations as well as a broader range of physical activities to ensure greater robustness and applicability of the model. These conclusions emphasize the necessity for advanced data preprocessing methods for accurate classification of physical exercises and indicate the need for further validation of these approaches across diverse contexts.

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Conflict of interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table A1 Characteristics of individual movement tasks

Title	Description
4x 10m Shuttle Run	Two cones (≥ 20 cm high) are placed 10 m apart and secured to the floor; their positions are marked with tape. From the start line, the participant sprints to the far cone, circles it on the left, returns to the start cone, and circles it on the right. This out-and-back pattern continues until the fourth touch. On the final return the athlete crosses the start line and run (at a comfortable pace) towards the next station.
Crawling	Immediately after the start signal, the participant lies prone and crawls forward for 10 m; the torso must remain in constant contact with the mat. The task terminates ≤ 1 m before the section finish. Crawling only on hands and knees is not permitted.
Progressive Cone Shuttle Run	Five cones are aligned longitudinally and taped to the floor. Cone A (the "return" cone) is 1 m from the start; the remaining cones are positioned at 2 m, 3 m, 4 m and 5 m, respectively. The participant runs from the start to cone 1, touches it, and returns to cone A. This sequence is repeated progressively to cones 2, 3 and 4, always touching the target cone with one hand and returning via the outside of the cones. After the final return, the participant circles around the entire set and proceeds directly to station 4.
Ring Collection and Placement Run	Six equal sections of a Swedish ladder are arranged alternately to the left and right of the line between the start and a cone 10 m distant; a loose ring is placed at the centre of each section. The participant runs the route and collects one ring from each part on the way to the cone, circles the cone, and returns along the same path, laying the rings. Rings must be placed (not thrown) onto the floor. From the final section the participant runs to station 5.
10x Position Change Drill	The exercise is performed on a mat. From an upright stance in the mat's centre, the participant completes ten cycles, each comprising: stand \rightarrow prone \rightarrow supine \rightarrow stand. All positions must be fully assumed. Upon finishing the tenth cycle, the participant proceeds immediately to station 6.
10x Head-to-Foot Hoop Crawl	Starting from standing, the participant completes ten cycles of head-to-feet crawling through a gymnastic hoop. Each cycle ends with the participant lying prone, stepping out of the hoop, standing upright, and re-entering. After the tenth cycle, the participant runs to station 7.
10x Bench Jumping	From the start the participant runs to the outer right edge of the bench and performs alternating single-leg jumps over the bench, landing on the opposite foot and briefly contacting the floor with both feet between jumps. Movement must be continuous and forward progressive. After the final jump, the participant sprints to the finish line and receives the triple tap annotation.
Crawling (repeat)	This section replicates the initial crawling task at the same location. The finish line corresponds to station 3, which also marks the end of the entire course.